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BACHELOR'S DEGREE IN ENGLISH STUDIES

Epistemic Modal Verbs in the Novel *Under the Dome*: A Contrastive Analysis in English and Spanish

Submitted by Carlos Aldana Albiach

Supervised by Inmaculada Garnes Tarazona

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ABSTRACT

English has a category of modal verbs that express the speaker's point of view of a proposition, also called modality. Modality can be deontic (expression obligation) or epistemic (expressing the degree of possibility) (Vázquez Orta, 2010). The auxiliary or modal verbs precede the lexical verb and add the perspective of the speaker/writer. The goal of the present study is to analyze the translation of a set of epistemic modal verbs from English into Spanish in a narrative text. The analysis is a case study of Stephen King's novel *Under the dome*, and its Spanish version. This research combines both a qualitative and quantitative analysis to investigate the cross-language use of modal markers expressing possibility: *might, may, can, could, must*. The findings show that the translator chose a variety of strategies to translate the epistemic modal verbs, from an equivalent modal marker to expressions in Spanish that imply a different degree of certainty than the original English text.

KEYWORDS: English, Spanish, modal verbs, translation, epistemic modality

RESUMEN

El idioma inglés tiene una categoría de verbos modales que expresan el punto de vista del hablante sobre una proposición, también llamada modalidad. La modalidad puede ser deóntica (expresar obligación) o epistémica (expresar el grado de posibilidad) (Vázquez Orta, 2010). Los verbos auxiliares o modales preceden al verbo léxico y añaden la perspectiva del hablante/escritor. El objetivo del presente estudio es analizar la traducción de un conjunto de verbos modales epistémicos del inglés al español en un texto narrativo. El análisis es un estudio de caso de la novela de Stephen King, *Under The Dome*, y en su versión en español *La Cúpula*. Esta investigación combina un análisis tanto cualitativo como cuantitativo para investigar el uso translingüístico de marcadores modales que expresan posibilidad: *might, may, can, could, must*. Los hallazgos muestran que el traductor eligió una variedad de estrategias para traducir el verbo modal epistémico, desde un marcador modal

equivalente hasta expresiones en español que implican un grado de certeza diferente al del texto original en inglés.

PALABRAS CLAVE: inglés, español, verbos modales, traducción, modalidad epistémica

RESUM

L'anglès té una categoria de verbs modals que expressen el punt de vista del parlant sobre una proposició, també anomenada modalitat. La modalitat pot ser deòntica (expressar obligació) o epistèmica (expressar el grau de possibilitat) (Vázquez Orta, 2010). Els verbs auxiliars o modals precedeixen el verb lèxic i afegeixen la perspectiva del parlant/escriptor. L'objectiu del present estudi és analitzar la traducció d'un conjunt de verbs modals epistèmics de l'anglès a l'espanyol en un text narratiu. L'anàlisi és un estudi de cas de la novel·la de Stephen King, *Under The Dome*, i en la seva versió en espanyol *La Cúpula*. Aquesta investigació combina una anàlisi tant qualitativa com quantitativa per investigar l'ús translingüístic de marcadors modals que expressen la possibilitat: *might, may, can, could, must*. Els resultats mostren que el traductor va canviar una varietat d'estratègies per traduir el verb modal, des d'un marcador modal epistèmic equivalent fins a expressions en espanyol que impliquen un grau de certesa diferent del text original en anglès.

PARAULES CLAU: anglès, espanyol, verbs modals, traducció, modalitat epistèmica

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1. INTRODUCTION

Modality has been widely discussed in the literature due to its broad and abstract semantic category that includes the speakers' subjective point of view and their degree of certainty based on their commitment with the proposition (Palmer, 2014: 2, Nuyts, 2005: 1). The conceptualization of modality in the present paper follows the traditional classification that includes two subtypes of modality: deontic and epistemic. The first subtype of modality is associated with permission and obligation, whereas the second subtype refers to possibility or necessity (Bybee & Fleischman, 1995: 3). The verb *must* can encompass both types of interpretations as shown in the sentence *He must be at home*, which conveys epistemic reading when referring to possibility, and a deontic one when referring to obligation (Fischer, 2010).

When a message is conveyed, either orally or in written text, the meaning can vary depending both on the words used and the context in which the speech or text are uttered. In this sense, pragmatics is a discipline that studies language use and its context, i.e. the analysis of the meaning conveyed by the speaker and its interpretation by the receiver (Levinson, 1983; Yule and Widdowson, 1997). One of the areas of interest within pragmatics is the notion of subjectivity, or the speaker's evaluation, embedded in the use of some words or expressions (Baumgarten et al. 2001). According to Nuyts (2001), subjectivity is a dimension that involves the speaker's evaluation. In this sense, modality combines both pragmatic and semantic meaning and incorporates the speaker's opinion towards the content of a proposition (Palmer, 2014: 2; Šolienė 2016: 224; Nuyts, 2005: 1).

This study is primarily concerned with epistemic modality, as the notion of possibility (within a scale of certainty-uncertainty) in English-Spanish translation is the main focus of the analysis. Epistemic modality indicating possibility can be expressed with a variety of grammatical categories in English: adverbs (*maybe, perhaps, probably*) verb phrases (*I think, I suppose, I presume*) modal auxiliaries (*may, might, could, can, must*), adjectives (*likely, probable, possible*) (Coates, 1995: 58, Gabrielatos & McEnery, 2005: 314) as will be described in section 3.1. Nevertheless, different languages express this semantic/pragmatic domain with multiple linguistic forms. Spanish also has a set of epistemic modal adverbs and modal verbs, but unlike in English, where the group of modal verbs show a high degree of grammaticalization (Hopper and Traugott 2003), Spanish shows

a preference for the use of verb mood (indicative/subjunctive) to express epistemic modality. In Spanish there is a dual system of verb mood to signal the perspective of the speaker towards the degree of probability/certainty of a proposition and the degree of commitment with the assertion.

Translating modality has proven to be very challenging, because languages differ in the way they convey this abstract category that conveys the subjective point of view of the speaker (Bybee & Fleischman, 1995: 3). In the area of translation, modality has been extensively discussed, since the heterogeneous set of grammatical categories that can express this subjective stance differs from one language to another. In this sense, research on translation studies emphasizes the functionality of language (Moindjie and Ummu-Salmah, 2020: 339).

The goal of the present study is to analyze the translation of a set of epistemic modal verbs which express doubt from English into Spanish in a literary narrative text. To this end, this contrastive analysis examines both the frequency and types of expressions of modality in a corpus composed of one English text, the science fiction novel *Under the Dome* by Stephen King's, and its Spanish translation: *La Cúpula*. The focus of the study are five modal verbs expressing possibility: *might*, *may*, *can*, *could*, and *must*. These verbs have been classified on a continuum to represent the scale of gradable certainty, from very uncertain (*might*) to almost certain (*must*): *might* > *may* > *could* > *can* > *must* (Alexander, 1999). However, these modal verbs are commonly intensified by other grammatical items when they cooccur with other epistemic markers, as will be seen in the analysis. In order to meet the goal of this paper, the analysis will try to answer the following questions:

1. Which linguistic devices are employed in the translation of epistemic modal markers from English into Spanish?
2. Do these devices show a similar pattern in both languages?

The present research paper is organized as follows. The next section includes a description with the background of the author and the novel. The concept of epistemic modality and the grammatical categories employed in English and Spanish will be described in section 3. Section 4 discusses the literature review on cross-languages comparison of modality. Section 5 includes an explanation of the methodology that was used in the study. Section 6 presents the analysis of the translation of modal verbs from English into Spanish

in the literary work *Under the Dome*. The discussion and conclusions will be presented in the last section.

2. AUTHORSHIP AND NOVEL

This section offers a brief account of the author and the novel which are the focus of this study. Stephen King, 74, is an American author who has become a worldwide mystery books best-seller. With a BA and an undergraduate degree from the University of Maine, and in business since 1959, the writer, scriptwriter, director, and actor has become one of the most widely read authors of the 20th century. We owe King the beginning of an era of mystery and terror, since today's highest-grossing horror films, such as *IT*, *The Shining*, *Under The Dome* or *Carrie*, were adaptations of his novels. He is seen as a narrator of contemporary America, as his stories are related to the description of the country's society, politics, and identity (Magistrale, 2009).

Briefly summarized, *Under The Dome*, is a mystery novel by Stephen King set in a town called Chester's Mill, located in Maine (where King lived his college years). This town is isolated from the rest of the world by an invisible barrier to the human eyes. The appearance of this invisible layer in the form of a dome causes a n increasing number of deaths and accidents of the people in the town.

This novel also deals with a very important issue of the 21st century: environmental damage. The town is enveloped in a blue and happy world, which they cannot access. The dome that surrounds Chester's Mill is an allegory of the damage that human beings are causing to the planet on a daily basis. King criticizes that often times people and governments look the other way regarding the conservation of our planet. However, as a society we should take responsibility and mark a turning point towards a better world in which we care for the environment. In this sense, several authors (Brown, 2017) have pointed out that the author used the main and secondary characters of the work to convey his messages and ideas regarding this controversial issue. The characters are ordinary people very realistically represented who confront the situation differently (Brow, 2017).

Under The Dome, a science fiction work published in 2009, was later translated into Spanish in 2010. Its great success led to the creation of a mystery TV series in 2013 which increased the level of mystery in the book. A total of 9 editions have been published in Spanish.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK: MODALITY

As seen in the introduction, modality is a notion that refers to the subjectivity expressed by the speaker or writer and it conveys his/her evaluation of an event. Modality can be expressed with numerous linguistic resources, such as verbs, adverbs, adjectives or quantifiers. Bybee and Fleishman (1995) differentiate between epistemic from deontic modality. As mentioned in the introduction, the epistemic modality refers to probabilities and the deontic modality refers to obligation.

Epistemic modality has been the object of study by different authors from different perspectives: grammaticalization studies (Hopper and Traugott 2003, Fischer 2010; Pakendorf and Schalley, 2007), semantics (Ju et al., 2015; Hogeweg et al., 2009; Narrog, 2012), pragmatics (Gea, 2000; Vestraete, 2005; Hoyer, 2009), Language Acquisition (Papafragou, 1998; Ehrlich, 2005, Stephany, 1995; Ramat and Galès, 1995), or translation studies (Kranich, 2009; Sathachai and Kenny, 2019; Zupan, 2016; Jaskot and Wiltos, 2017) which will be the focus of this paper.

One of the problems in translation lies in the lack of lexical or grammatical equivalents among languages. As many other linguistic aspects, the expression of modality differs between English and Spanish. However, as claimed by Rabadán (2006: 161), English modals do not exactly match with a corresponding Spanish modal verb. English is an Anglo-Saxon language with a highly grammaticalized system of modal verbs, whereas Spanish is a Romance language which expresses epistemic modality with a system of indicative and subjunctive verbal mood and a group of modal verbs.

Modality can be expressed with the use of different grammatical categories, such as verbs, evaluative adjectives, evaluative nouns, modal adverbs, quantifiers, and hedging. According to Brennan (1993: 18), “epistemic modal sentences are those expressing possibility or necessity relative to some state of knowledge.” However, the scope of modality goes beyond the sentence level and it should be considered in its discursive context (Hoyer, 2009: 101). In this sense, modal auxiliaries in English are a category of verbs that indicate the stance of the speaker regarding possibility or necessity (Palmer, 2003: 3, Mitkovska and Buzarovska, 2014: 197).

The notion of epistemic modality has been defined as a continuum of certainty, from complete certainty to complete uncertainty, with a dimension of different degrees of

probability (Nuyts 2006: 6). The sentence in example (1) from the novel which is the focus of this research illustrates this notion:

(1) English: **Maybe**, but **can** I tell you something my mother used to say?

Spanish: *Quizá, pero, ¿quieres que te diga lo que decía mi madre?*

Example (1) shows that modal verbs are the markers of epistemic modality both in Spanish and in English. However, there are other epistemic modality markers such as adverbs or hedging, as will be seen in the next subsections. For example, the modal verb *can* is combined with the epistemic adverb *maybe* in example (1) above and it has been translated as the construction *quieres que* into Spanish.

Regarding hedging, it has been described as a politeness strategy (Myers, 1989) with which the speaker shows a degree of certainty/uncertainty with the proposition (Crompton: 274). For example, Martín Martín (2000 y 2001) observed that in academic writing the use of hedging was used as a strategy to mark a doubtful attitude or attention on the part of the author towards the reader.

The following subsections describe the different linguistic devices employed to express epistemic modality in English and in Spanish. Both languages have a set of modal verbs, adverbs, adjectives and other tools that convey the speaker's stance. However, these languages differ in the frequency of use of each category. English shows a preference for the use of modal verbs, whereas Spanish has a productive system of adverbs and verbal mood to express the different degrees of certainty.

3.1. English epistemic modality

As mentioned before, modality is a cover term related to the subjectivity expressed by the issuer in a text. It expresses the attitude of the author, who expresses his feelings towards the other interlocutors and other elements in the context (Gil-Salom and Soler-Monreal, 2014). Modality can be expressed with numerous linguistic resources in English, such as discourse markers, adverbs, verbs, adjectives, nouns, or quantifying particles (Brinton, 2000).

- a) Modal verbs: *can, must, should, might, may, could, will, shall, would, be able to*, etc. (Brinton, 2000: 149)
- b) Semi-modal verbs: *need to, supposed to*, etc. (Facchinetti et al., 2003)

- c) Evaluative adjectives: *possible, probable, certain, uncertain, evident*, etc. (Nuyts, 1999: 105)
- d) Evaluative nouns: *possibility, probability, certainty, uncertainty, evidence, doubt, necessity*, etc. (Hohaus and Schulze 2020: 269)
- e) Modal adverbs: *likely, maybe, perhaps, possibly, supposedly, presumably, evidently, certainly, surely*, etc. (Rozumko, 2017: 76)
- f) Verbal quantifiers: *I think, I suppose, I guess, I believe*, etc. (Givón, 1993: 38)
- g) Discourse markers: *In fact, actually, indeed*, etc. (Rozumko, 2021)
- h) Conditional clauses: *If, provided that, unless* (Suhadi, 2011: 160).

All these linguistic categories express subjectivity on the part of the speaker, as they can all express epistemic modality. However, English shows a preference for the use of modal verbs. This category of verbs shares several syntactic and semantic characteristics; they are all auxiliary verbs that precede a lexical verb, they cannot be inflected, and they cannot cooccur (Palmer, 2012).

3.2. Spanish epistemic modality

As in English, modality is also present in Spanish to convey the subjectivity of the speaker and the degree of commitment with a proposition. However, apart from modal verbs, Spanish employs other resources to express the semantic notion that includes the attitude or thoughts of the speaker, such as verbal mood or adverbs.

- a) Adverbs: *quizás, tal vez, acaso, a lo mejor, igual, probablemente, posiblemente*, etc. (Cornillie, 2010)
- b) Modal verbs: *Poder, deber (de), tener que* (Cornillie, 2008)
- c) Semi-auxiliaries: *Parecer, resultar* (Cornillie, 2008)
- d) Lexical verbs: *creer, pensar, dudar, suponer* (Saeger, 2006)
- e) Verb Mood: Spanish distinguishes between indicative and subjunctive mood (Barrios, 2016: 261; Lunn, 1995)
- f) Verbal constructions: *Es posible que, seguro que, puede ser, es probable que* (Barrios, 2016: 261)
- g) Discourse markers: *por lo visto, al parecer* (Cornillie and Gras, 2020)
- h) Verb mood: indicative versus subjunctive (Hirota, 2021).

In Spanish, not only can modal verbs be combined with other lexical and morphological items, but also, in contrast with English, they can be inflected in tense, aspect and mood (Cornillie, 2008). Nonetheless, one of the most productive devices to express epistemic modality in Spanish is verbal mood. Like in many other Romance Languages, the indicative-subjunctive mood system is a grammatical resource for the expression of epistemic modality in Spanish (Lunn, 1995). The subjunctive mood is used in Spanish by speakers to evaluate the value of a sentence. In the morphological level, the subjunctive mood distinguishes between present and past tense, and a future tense, now mainly relegated to legal texts. In the syntax level, the Spanish subjunctive appears in subordinate clauses in which the speakers show their non-assertion towards the proposition (Lunn, 1995; Cornillie 2008, Nordström, 2010), as in:

(2) Dudo que **sea** buena idea. (Lunn, 1995)

(3) Es probable que **venga**.

(4) ¿Crees que **haya** leído el libro?

The subjunctive mood can be usually combined with other devices of epistemic modality, such as adverbs (*probablemente, posiblemente*), expressions (*puede ser que*) (Hirota, 2021) or a category of verbs that appear in the main clause and that trigger the use of the subjunctive (*dudar, creer, pensar*).

(5) **yo creo** que **es probable** que a final de año la política monetaria **pueda** funcionar [...] (Saeger, 2006: 270).

With lexical verbs, such as *creer, dudar, suponer* or *pensar*, the speaker expresses his/her beliefs, as in example (7).

(6) **Yo creo** que el gobierno ha llevado con gran habilidad la reforma política.” (Saeger 2006: 3)

On the other hand, the subjunctive mood is not as productive in English as it is in Spanish. Apart from that, the morphology of the subjunctive mood in English is not easily identified, as in (7), unless the morphological inflection of the third person singular is absent as in (8):

(7) It is necessary that they **receive** (subj.) it by tomorrow. (Whatley, 2013: 3)

(8) It is important that he **think** (subj.). (Whatley, 2013: 3)

In English, there are also certain verbs and expressions that trigger the subjunctive mood, such as: *it is important that, it is essential that, I suggest that* (Aarts, 2012).

4. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Ekasani et al. (2018: 73), “translation is the process of transferring the meaning of a text from a source language (SL) into the target language (TL).” However, often times, the SL and the TL do not share linguistic devices to express the same semantic notions. In this sense, as previously seen in section 3, modality is related to the subjectivity expressed in a proposition, as it is linked to the speaker’s stance (Ramón 2009: 75). As usually occurs with other expressions of subjectivity, modality is an abstract notion that encompasses different degrees of probability and that can be expressed by means of several linguistic devices. As stated by Vazquez-Orta (2010: 80), “[b]y means of modal expressions the writer can evaluate a particular situation in terms of possibility, probability, permission, volition, obligation and necessity. A vast amount of literature has explored cross-linguistic modality and the behavior of modal verbs in different languages. This section presents a description of the previous research about epistemic modality in translation and the challenges it poses for translators. For example, a study on contrastive epistemic modality by Aijmer (1997) analyzed the different syntactic and semantic patterns of this type of modality in English and in Swedish in order to explain the problems that some Swedish epistemic particles posed for translators, because of their additional pragmatic meaning that indexes the interlocutors in the communicative process in their function as discourse markers.

Regarding the comparison between English and Spanish, as it is the object of this study, Ramón (2006) contrasted the epistemic modality in English and Spanish based on two corpora (Cobuild/Bank of English and Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual). The goal of her analysis was the comparison of two equivalent adverbs: *probably* and *probablemente* in order to examine the actual use of these words in the two languages, both syntactically and lexically. The author highlights that the use of *probably* in English is less used as an adverbial than Spanish *probablemente*, mainly because English relies on a group of modal verbs to express epistemic meaning, whereas Spanish relies more on verb tense and mood, among other strategies.

In a latter study, Ramón (2009) studied the translation of epistemic adverbs from English into Spanish and compared three English adverbs (namely, *certainly*, *probably* and *possibly*) with their translated Spanish version in a corpus of different book genres. Her study

revealed that the analyzed modal adverbs are usually omitted in the Spanish translations when they appear with other modal verbs. The author concludes that this might be due to the high level of grammaticalization of these epistemic adverbs in English. She also observed that the translation of these adverbs can be a very challenging task due to their multifunctionality in English.

In a corpus-based study of academic texts published in the area of psychology, Martín (2000, 2001) also observed differences in the linguistic devices used to express epistemic modality and a certain degree of cross-cultural variation in the frequency of epistemic modality in English and Spanish texts. English texts showed a higher degree of modal markers as a rhetorical tool to mitigate the degree of assertion of their claims. On the other hand, Spanish texts included less modal markers. This might be due, according to the author, to the low risk of peer criticism from a more reduced audience, as most papers in the area of psychology are published in English for a bigger impact. Another reason that the author points out could be that Spanish writers do not regard the use of modal hedges as inherent to academic Spanish.

Similarly, a study carried out in by Carrió Pastor (2012) examined epistemic modal verbs and expressions in research papers written in English, both by native speakers and by non-native speakers (with Spanish as their L1). The author observed that the corpus of papers written by English native speakers contained a high frequency of epistemic modal verbs, such as *may*, to mitigate the authors' research claims, whereas the non-native speakers often included the modal verbs *must* and *can*, which might be due to a direct translation of *puede*.

Another study by Alonso-Almeida (2014) compared epistemic devices in research papers' abstracts written in English and Spanish in different fields (medicine, computing, and law). The analysis focused on modal verbs, nouns, lexical verbs and other devices that express epistemic meaning. The findings showed that English abstracts contained more epistemic devices, such as modal verbs, than the Spanish texts. The author concluded that the texts written in English used more epistemic strategies for pragmatic effects, such as to mitigate the author's claims and to show more politeness.

Regarding the translation of modality into other languages, more recently the study by Zupan (2016) aimed to analyze the epistemic modality in the translation from English into Slovene of *The Fall of the House of Usher*, by the American poet Edgar Allan Poe. Zupan's

study focuses on adverbs such as *perhaps*, *possibly*, and clauses such as *I thought* or *I fancied* to show the different resources for the translation of epistemic modality used in this narrative into Slovenian. The results of the study show that there are some translation changes regarding the use of epistemic modality. He pointed out that the translation was missing or had changes in some cases, such as the use of non-modalized propositions, which affects the global meaning of the proposition. In this sense, the narrator's point of view is ignored, which, according to the author, has some type of effect on the narrative.

Another language that has been compared to English in translation studies is German. Kranich (2009) investigated the translation of epistemic modal verbs (*might*, *may*, *can* and *must*) in a corpus of texts. The author observed that the translation of modal verbs could be an equivalent verb. However, a non-verbal equivalent was more frequently chosen in German (adverbs, adjectives and modal particles). The author observed that whenever the modal verb was not literally translated, the result was a different lexical strategy that expressed a higher level of certainty than the English modal verb. In this sense, the degree of epistemicity was also different in the SL and in the TL.

Šolienė (2007) conducted a pilot study on the comparison of modal verbs in English (*might*, *could*, and *may*) and modal adverbs (such as *perhaps* and *maybe*) with their Lithuanian equivalents by using a parallel corpus. As expected, the researcher observed that both languages vary regarding the use of modal verbs and the resources used to convey epistemic modality. English relies mainly on auxiliary modal verbs, whereas Lithuanian depends more on non-verbal forms, such as adverbs or particles.

Epistemic modality in English has also been compared to Polish. Koźbiał (2020) investigated this type of modality in legal and institutional texts. The author used a parallel English and Polish corpus to show the different pattern of modality in both languages and observed that judges in both languages depend greatly on the use of epistemic modality to justify the facts expressed. One difference that was noticed by the author between English and Polish was that the latter relies more on modal adverbs and particles.

Another study that focused on academic languages was conducted by Martikainen (2018). In this case, the author compared the use of modal markers in English and French abstracts in the medical field. She observed the translation was frequently distorted when

auxiliary and evidential verbs preceded by modal adjectives and adverbs, which led to a different interpretation on the part of the readers.

As these studies show, English has a system of highly grammaticalized modal verbs to express the speaker's subjectivity that are not always equivalent to the group of modal verbs in the TL, so the latter needs to use other linguistic devices to express the same semantic notion. Translators tend to use non-equivalent translations in order to map the semantic meaning of modality in the SL and the TL. However, sometimes the translator chooses to change both the grammatical and semantic element of the SL, which may lead to an important change in meaning in the TL.

5. METHODOLOGY

As mentioned before, the main goal of this study is to provide a description of the epistemic modal verbs which express possibility in a corpus of texts translated from English into Spanish and to observe the different degrees of certainty expressed by the chosen linguistic devices.

In order to analyze the translation of modal verbs, the data for the analysis was collected from two literary texts, the English novel *Under the Dome*, by Stephen King and its Spanish translation *La Cúpula*. The English text contains a total of 332,958 words and the Spanish text consists of a corpus of 368,143 words.

The methodology selected to conduct the analysis combines both quantitative and qualitative methods. The analysis includes information about the frequency of the different modal verbs and the types of linguistic devices present in the Spanish translation. All the examples of *might*, *may*, *can*, *could* and *must* were extracted manually by using the search engine in the PDF documents. All the numbers of tokens were inserted into a file and no samples were discarded initially, although negative contractions were not considered in the analysis.

Next, the qualitative method was used to examine the uses of modal verbs and the translation resources employed by the translator of the Spanish version. A close reading of the two texts was carried out to examine parallelisms and differences in the use of modality. It is also worth noting that due to the big number of occurrences, the different readings (deontic or epistemic) of the verb *must* were not separated.

The comparison of modal devices in Spanish and English in the selected corpus can provide new insight on translation phenomena regarding modality. Due to the lack of technological devices needed for the simultaneous parallel comparison of the two languages, and the arduous task of a manual extraction, some examples of *could* corresponding to different conjugations of the Spanish verb *poder* were included in *other categories* in the analysis.

6. ANALYSIS

Based on the corpus of the English and Spanish version of *Under the Dome*, this section presents the results of the analysis and the frequency of appearance of each modal verb with its corresponding translations. The data have been classified according to the different modal verbs under consideration that were extracted from the English text: *might* (611 cases), *could* (817 cases), *can* (519 cases), *may* (124 cases), and *must* (100 cases). These modal verbs, as previously mentioned, indicate capacity, ability, and different degrees of certainty and probability. Each modal verb was compared to its Spanish translation and some examples were extracted to illustrate the different choices that were used by the translator in the Spanish version. The first modal verb extracted from the corpus and compared in the English and Spanish texts was *might*:

<i>MIGHT</i>		
SPANISH TRANSLATION	TOKENS	PERCENTAGE
<i>PODRÍA</i>	210	34.36 %
<i>QUIZÁS</i>	105	17.18 %
<i>PROBABLEMENTE</i>	86	14 %
<i>POSIBLEMENTE</i>	23	3.76 %
OTHER FORMS	187	30 %
TOTAL	611	

Table 1: Translations of the modal verb *might* from English into Spanish.

As Table 1 shows, the modal verb *might* has been translated in the Spanish version as *podría* in most of the cases (34.36%), as shown in the following example:

- (9) English: She **might** cost Andy Sanders some real money before long; she loved the Seneca, and had expressed a desire to have one just like it, [...]

Spanish: *A Andy Sanders eso **podría** costarle una fortuna dentro de poco; a su mujer le encantaba el Seneca y había expresado su deseo de tener uno igual que aquel pero nuevo, [...]*

Example (9) indicates a hypothesis about some future event expressed with the epistemic marker *might*. As seen in Table 1, the translator has chosen the translation of *might* as the modal equivalent *podría* in 210 occurrences. The second most frequent translation is *quizás/quizá* in 17.18% of cases, with 105 tokens, as in the example (10):

(10) English: wondering to herself what Horace Greeley would have thought of a world where picking up dogshit from the gutter was not just socially expected but a legal responsibility. She thought he **might** have shot himself.

Spanish: *preguntándose qué habría pensado Horace Greeley de un mundo en el que la sociedad no solo esperaba que recogieras mierdas de perro de la cuneta, sino que era una responsabilidad legal. Quizás pensó que se habría pegado un tiro.*

Example (10) also conveys probability, but this time about a past action. The translator chose the adverb *quizá/quizás* instead of the verbal form *podría*. As seen in the section on Spanish modality, this language tends to express epistemic modality with a set of adverbial markers. This can also be observed in the next most frequent translations in Table 1, such as *probablemente* and *posiblemente*. Regarding *probablemente* it appeared in the corpus in a 14%, with a total of 86 occurrences, as shown in the example (11):

(11) English: Barbie guessed the older guys **might** be scientists from NSA.

Spanish: *Barbie supuso que los chicos mayores probablemente fueran científicos de la NSA.*

In example (11) the speaker is expressing probability based on one of the characters' deductions. Both linguistic devices (modal verb *might* and adverb *probablemente*) convey a certain degree of certainty with which the speaker is assessing the truth of a given fact. In English, the use of *might* appears in the sentence with another lexical verb that expresses epistemic modality (*guessed*). In Spanish, the adverb is included with the translation of the epistemic lexical verb *supuso*. In addition, the Spanish version combines the use of the adverb *probablemente* with the imperfect subjunctive of the verb *ser* (*fuera*) to intensify the uncertainty of a hypothesis about an event.

The fourth most frequent translation found in the text was *posiblemente*, which also indicates possibility in Spanish. This adverb has been used a total of 23 times in the translation, and in 3.76% of cases, as in the following example:

- (12) English: I **might** be able to play hooky for an hour. No promises
Spanish: *Posiblemente consiga escaquearme una hora. No te prometo nada.*

Example (12) refers to a hypothetical situation in which the speaker expresses his degree of commitment with a future event. He is not fully committing with the assertion with the use of the modal verb *might* in the English version. On the other hand, in the Spanish translation, example (12) includes a combination of the verbal construction *posiblemente* and the subjunctive form of the verb *conseguir* (*consiga*) to convey the speaker's stance. The speaker expresses uncertainty and does not fully commit with the assertion.

In addition, the modal verb *might* has been translated with other forms in 30% of the cases (categorized as *other forms* in Table 1). Some of these translations are other verbal forms and adverbial locutions such as *tal vez*, as shown in example (13):

- (13) English: There is no love in her voice when she speaks; no regret or remorse. But there **might** be pity.
Spanish: *No hay cariño en su voz cuando habla; tampoco arrepentimiento ni remordimientos. Pero tal vez haya compasión.*

Another adverbial translation of *might* in the corpus of the two texts is the adverbial locution *a lo mejor*, which indicates uncertainty of an event indicated in the proposition, as seen in example (14):

- (14) English: Did he have this to look forward to until he was forty-five or so, when Dr. Haskell said they **might** let up?
Spanish: *¿De verdad debía resignarse a convivir con aquello hasta que cumpliera los cuarenta y cinco, que era cuando el doctor Haskell le había dicho que las migrañas a lo mejor remitían?*

A lo mejor is an adverbial locution in Spanish employed to convey probability and the degree of uncertainty of the speaker towards an event or action. *Quizá/s* is another adverb that conveys the epistemic stance of the speaker and his/her evaluation regarding the degree of certainty of an event as in example (15):

(15) English: Don't be so pessimistic. The Dome **might** blow out to sea tonight.

Spanish: *No seas tan pesimista. Quizá la Cúpula desaparezca esta noche.*

This epistemic adverbial is equivalent to English *maybe*, but as seen in example (15), the translator of *Under the Dome* has chosen *quizá* to translate the modal verb *might*.

As seen in section 3.1., Spanish has a system of epistemic adverbials to express the speaker's uncertainty towards a proposition. Other linguistic devices employed in Spanish for the same purposes are the set of verbal constructions that trigger the use of the subjunctive mood (*es probable que, es posible que*) which have also been used by the translator of *Under the Dome*:

(16) English: Parsonage **might** be unlocked, too, but right now I **might** be able to use him.

Spanish: *Es probable que su casa tampoco esté cerrada con llave pero ahora mismo es probable que lo necesite.*

In example (16) the speaker is expressing uncertainty about a fact with the verb *might*. In Spanish, the two modal verbs (*might*) are translated with the verbal construction *es probable que* combined with the verbs of the subordinate clause in the subjunctive form (*esté* and *necesite*).

The two corpora of literary texts show that *might* has been translated with different devices from English into Spanish to express probability while keeping the pragmatic aspects of epistemic meanings. However, in some other instances, the probability conveyed by *might* is not found in the translated version, as can be seen in example (17):

(17) English: No matter how beautiful this particular day, winter was lurking a page or two over on the calendar. The south **might** be good.

Spanish: *Por muy bonito que fuera ese día en concreto, el invierno acechaba a solo una o dos páginas del calendario. El sur tenía buena pinta.*

In example (18) there is no trace of a possibility or uncertainty interpretation, although the sentence includes the speaker's opinion of a place (*The south*).

The next modal verb extracted from the corpus was *may*, and the frequency of the different translations can be seen in Table 2 below:

MAY		
SPANISH TRANSLATION	TOKENS	PERCENTAGE
<i>PODER</i>	82	66,12 %
<i>ES POSIBLE</i>	20	16,12 %
<i>PUEDE SER QUE</i>	2	1'61 %
OTHER FORMS	20	16,12 %
TOTAL	124	

Table 2: Translations of the modal verb *may* from English into Spanish.

As the Table 2 shows, the modal verb *may* has been translated in different verbal forms and locutions such as *poder*, *puede ser que*, y *es posible*. Firstly, the modal verb *may* has been translated in its Spanish version as *poder*. This word appears in 66.12% of a total of 82 cases. Example (20) illustrates the context of use of the most frequent translation:

(20) English: I hope your first aid skills are up to snuff, Pammie, because you **may** have to use them.

Spanish: *Espero que tengas frescos tus conocimientos de primeros auxilios, Pammie, porque a lo mejor vas a poder ponerlos en práctica.*

Example (20) indicates possibility of a future event; however, the Spanish translation combines the semantic meaning of ability of the verb *poder* with the epistemic pragmatic reading of *possibility* with the use of *a lo mejor*.

The third category of translation that is included in Table 2 is *puede ser que*. These words only appear in 2 examples in the entire work. Thus, the percentage of appearance is 1.61%. An example of this type of translation is illustrated in example (21):

(21) English: We **may** not like it, we **may** not always think they're worth it, but it's the job God gave us.

Spanish: *Puede ser que no nos guste, puede que no siempre creamos que lo merecen, pero es la labor que Dios nos ha encomendado.*

Example (21) indicates probability. The two cases of the verb *may* have been translated as *puede ser que* and *puede que* in the example above.

The third frequent translation found in the work is *es possible*, which appears a total of 20 times in the work, with a percentage of 16.12%. An example of this is shown below:

(22) English: Walk around back with me, Mr. Barbara. I **may** invite you in later on, but not until I'm sure of you.

Spanish: Acompáñeme al jardín trasero, señor Barbara. **Es posible** que lo **evite** a entrar más adelante, pero esperaré a estar convencida de que puedo confiar en usted.

Example (22) indicates probability, both in English and Spanish. As can be observed, Spanish combines again a verbal construction (*es posible*) with the use of the subjunctive mood of the verb *evitar* (*evite*). The speaker expresses her judgement in the proposition explicitly, in this case a low degree of certainty, when she later adds *esperaré a estar convencida*.

(23) English: He scrubbed the wound with sterile saline, debrided, then trimmed with his trusty no. 10 scalpel. “Six stitches with my very best four-oh nylon.”

“Awesome,” the kid said. Then: “I think I **may** hurl.

Spanish: *Frotó la herida con solución salina aséptica, desbridó y luego cortó con su fiel escalpelo n.º 10—. Seis puntos con mi mejor nailon cuatro-cero.*

*Genial —dijo el chico. Después—: Creo que **a lo mejor** devuelvo.*

The use of *a lo mejor* combined with *creo* in example (23) conveys the point of view and judgement of the speaker towards a fact. The speaker expresses his opinion about the degree of likelihood about his assertion.

The next modal verb extracted from the corpus was *could*. As Table 3 shows, the modal verb *could* has been translated mostly with different verbal forms of the verb *poder* in the Spanish version, such as *podría ser*, *pudiera*, *podrías*, *pudimos*, *podríamos*, *se podría*, and *podría haber*.

COULD		
SPANISH TRANSLATION	TOKENS	PERCENTAGE
<i>PUDIERA</i>	121	14.81 %
<i>PODRÍA HABER</i>	44	5.38 %
<i>PODRÍA SER</i>	34	4.16%
<i>PODRÍAS</i>	22	2.69 %
<i>PODRÍAMOS</i>	22	2.69 %
<i>PUDIMOS</i>	2	0.24 %
<i>SE PODRÍA</i>	2	0.24%
OTHER FORMS	570	69.76 %
TOTAL	817	

Table 3: Translations of the modal verb *could* from English into Spanish.

Table 3 shows the frequency of the different translations of the modal verb *could*. It has been translated in the conditional form (*podría ser, podría, podríamos*) in 15.16% of cases, as in the following examples from the literary corpus:

- (24) English: Peter Randolph was a fair cop, and he **could** be just as hard as he needed to be, but Duke didn't like him.
 Spanish: *Peter Randolph era un buen agente, y **podría** ser todo lo duro que hiciera falta, pero a Duke no le caía bien.*
- (25) English: Maybe we **could** have a Dome Sale. You know what they say—when life hands you lemons, make lemonade.
 Spanish: *Quizá **podríamos** organizar las Rebajas de la Cúpula. Ya sabes lo que dicen, cuando la vida te da limones, haz limonada.*
- (26) English: Frotó la herida con solución salina aséptica, desbridó y luego cortó con su fiel escalpelo n.º 10—. Seis puntos con mi mejor nailon cuatro-cero. He **could** have been a statue except for the single vein pulsing in the center of his forehead.
 Spanish: *Randolph, el intrépido jefe de policía del pueblo, seguía sentado con las manos plantadas en sus carnosos muslos. **Podría** haber pasado por una estatua de no ser por el palpitar de una vena en mitad de la frente.”*

Example (25) indicates a hypothetical situation about an event. In this case despite the possibility that Peter may be hard, the other character, Duke, was not fond of him. This supposition effect is kept in the Spanish version. In example (25), the combination of the modal verb *podríamos* with the adverb *quizás* emphasizes the subjectivity of the message about a future event. In this case, the speaker expresses doubt about a future event and the possibility of organizing an event. Example (26) refers to a possibility in the past. Randolph, one of the characters, is standing still after a shooting in the Town Hall. He is immobile like a statue.

The second most frequent translation is the subjunctive form *podiera* with a 14.81% percentage of cases with a total of 121 tokens. The following example shows the above statement:

(27) English: Before Rusty **could** say anything, his cell phone rang.

Spanish: *Antes de que Rusty **podiera** contestar, sonó su teléfono.*

Example (27) indicates both capacity and possibility, however, the use of the subjunctive form includes epistemic modality in the utterance. As it was indicated in the theoretical section on modality, Spanish makes use of a dual category of verbal mood, indicative and subjunctive, to express modality.

Other conjugations of the verb could appear in the imperfect tense in Spanish.

(28) English: They **could** have missed breaks, Barbie knew that was possible—holes the size of windows or doors—but he doubted it.

Spanish: ***Podían** haber pasado por alto alguna brecha, Barbie sabía que era posible, agujeros del tamaño de una ventana o una puerta, pero lo dudaba.*

The epistemic modality in example (28) is observed by the use of the perfect tense of the verb *could* combined with the expression *but he doubted it*. The Spanish translation keeps the original epistemic meaning in which the speaker is evaluating the probability of a past event.

Another infrequent translation found in the corpus of texts is the verbal form in the preterit *podimos* with a percentage of 0.24% and a total of 2 cases in the entire work. However, the examples analyzed in the Spanish version refer to the ability to do something, instead of uncertainty or possibility (epistemic modality).

Most of the other 570 forms in Table 3 correspond to different conjugations of the verb *poder* in Spanish. However, the Spanish epistemic expression *puede que* has also been found as a linguistic device to translate *could* in the perfect tense as in (29):

(29) English: And for the first time in maybe four years (it **could** have been longer), he kissed his father’s cheek.

Spanish: *Y por primera vez en cuatro años (puede que más), le dio un beso la mejilla a su padre.*

In example (29), the use of *could* in English and the translation of *puede que* in Spanish creates a degree of uncertainty when the speaker is not fully confident about the assertion.

The next modal verb extracted from the corpus was *can*, and the frequency of the different translations can be seen in Table 4 below.

CAN		
SPANISH TRANSLATION	TOKENS	PERCENTAGE
<i>PUEDO</i>	124	23,89 %
<i>PODER</i>	117	22,54 %
<i>PODEMOS</i>	94	18,11%
<i>PUEDES</i>	78	15,02 %
OTHER FORMS	106	20,42 %
TOTAL	519	

Table 4: Translations of the modal verb *can* from English into Spanish.

As Table 4 shows, the modal verb *can* has mostly been translated in different forms of the paradigm of the verb *poder*, such as: *podemos*, *poder*, *puedo*, and *puedes*. Firstly, the modal verb *can* has been frequently translated into its Spanish version as the first person plural form of the present tense of the verb *poder* (*podemos*). This word appears in 18.11% of a total of 94 cases, as in the following example:

(30) English: As soon as Rommie and Jackie had returned to the top floor, the two men began to holler. “Let’s get out of here while we still **can**,” Ernie said.

Spanish: En cuanto Rommie y Jackie volvieron arriba, los dos jóvenes empezaron a vociferar.

*—Salgamos de aquí ahora que todavía **podemos** —dijo Ernie.*

Example (30) indicates capacity or ability to perform an action. Two characters are talking about the possibility of escaping jail.

The second most frequent translation of this modal verb is the infinitive of the verb *poder*, with 117 cases and a 22.54% of occurrence, as in example (31):

(31) English: And you need to wait to hear from me before you **can** talk to anybody else.

*Spanish: Y tiene que esperar a recibir noticias más antes de **poder** hablar con alguien más.*

Example (31) also indicates capacity or ability to perform an action. The infinitive form of the verbs has to do with its grammatical context as an auxiliary verb.

The third translation of this modal verb is the first person singular in the present tense *puedo* in Table 3, which appears 124 times, and a total of 23.89% percentage of appearance, as in the following example:

(32) English: I **can** be a bitch myself, when I have to be. Brenda too, if she gets her back up.

*Spanish: **Puedo** ser una zorra cuando es necesario. Brenda También, si la ponen de mala leche.*

Example (32) indicates lack of certainty of the speaker about a proposition. The modal verb *can* refers to possibility and has been translated in the Spanish version as the subjective form of the verb *poder* (*pueda*).

(33) English: The chuck planned (so far as a woodchuck **can** be said to plan anything) to head back into the woods long before he got that far.

*Spanish: La marmota había planeado (en la medida en que **pueda** decirse que una marmota haya planeado nada) volver a internarse en la vegetación mucho antes de llegar tan lejos*

The use of the subjunctive in the Spanish version includes the degree of uncertainty of the speaker.

The fourth frequent translation is the second person singular form in the present tense *puedes*, which also indicates the ability to perform an action. This word appears 78 times translated in its Spanish version throughout the work, and a 15.02% percentage of appearance. An example of this can be seen in (34):

(34) English: I hope not. **Can** you go in and cover? I bet the place is standing there empty and unlocked.

Spanish: *Espero que no. ¿Puedes ir a cubrir comisaría? Apuesto a que se ha quedado vacía y abierta.*

Example (34) indicates ability or capacity semantically. However, it is included in a question, so it is actually expressing a request if the pragmatic context is taken into account.

The last modal verb extracted from the corpus was *must*, and the frequency of the different translations can be seen in Table 5 below.

MUST		
SPANISH TRANSLATION	TOKENS	PERCENTAGE
<i>TENER QUE</i>	41	41 %
<i>DEBEMOS</i>	23	23 %
<i>DEBO</i>	17	17 %
<i>DEBEN</i>	17	17 %
OTHER FORMS	2	2 %
TOTAL	100	

Table 5: Translations of the modal verb *must* from English into Spanish.

As Table 5 shows, the modal verb *must* has been translated in different forms of the Spanish modal verbs *deber* and *tener que*: *debo*, *debemos*, *deben* and *tener que*. The frequency of the verb *deber* is 77% when the different conjugations are combined. The examples below illustrate the most frequent translations of this modal verb:

(34) English: “What happened?” She asked. “I **must** have fallen asleep. I had a dream, only I can’t remember what it was.”

Spanish: *¿Qué ha pasado? – preguntó-. Debo de haberme quedado dormida. He tenido un sueño, pero no recuerdo qué era.*

The use of the first person singular in the present tense appears in 17% with a total of 17 cases. Example (34) indicates an evidence that the speaker has about a past event.

The second most frequent translation of this modal verb is *debemos*, with a 23% of cases (23 examples) illustrated in example (35):

(35) English: And the line he remembered most clearly was the one about how in a small town “we all **must** know our place.”

Spanish: *Y la frase que mejor recordaba era la que decía que en un pequeño pueblo “todos **debemos** saber cuál es nuestro sitio”.*

The third most frequent translation in its Spanish version is the third person plural form in the present tense *deben*, which was found in the text in 17 tokens (17% of cases). An example of this of this use can be found in (36):

(36) English: Then so **must** they.

Spanish: *Pues ellos también **deben** oírlo.*

The fourth frequent translation is *tener que* that in its Spanish version. This verbal construction appears 41 times throughout the work, with a 41% of appearance. Example (37) shows the context of use of this translation:

(37) English: Honey, this setup **must** have cost a fortune!

Spanish: *¡Cariño, este montaje ha **tenido que** costar una fortuna!*

Again, the translation of the modal verb *must* from English into Spanish shows a preference to keep an equivalent modal verb (*deber* or *tener que*). In example (37) the speaker expresses her high degree of certainty about a fact with the use of the modal verb *must*. As mentioned in the introduction, the modal verb *must* is used to convey a higher degree of certainty towards a proposition than other modal verbs, which in Spanish are commonly translated as *deber* and *tener que*.

Unlike English, Spanish differentiates syntactically between the use of *deber* as an epistemic modal verb and as a deontic modal verb. For example, the verb *deber* followed by infinitive has a deontic meaning which expresses obligation, whereas the verb *deber* followed by the preposition *de* and an infinitive convey epistemic meaning (Schulte and Arroyo, 2014), as in example (38):

(38) English: She **must** have crossed over the Chester’s Mill town line minutes (or even seconds) before the border slammed shut.

Spanish: ***Debió de** cruzar los límites de Chester's Mills unos minutos (o incluso segundos) antes de que la frontera se cerrara de golpe.*

The translation of the English text in example (38) keeps the original epistemic meaning of the degree of certainty towards an event. However, in some other cases, the epistemic meaning is not conveyed in the Spanish translation as can be observed in example (39):

(39) English: I she had reconsidered, everything in his life thereafter would have changes. Because she **must** have made it out; he never saw the fresh-faced blonde or the dirty old Ford F-150 again.

Spanish: *Si ella de verdad lo hubiera reconsiderado, todo habría cambiado a partir de entonces en la vida de Barbie. Porque ella **había conseguido** escapar; él jamás volvió a ver ni a la rubia atractiva, ni la vieja furgoneta Ford F-150.*

As seen in example (39), the speaker (in this case the narrator) is evaluating an event and showing a degree of certainty because there is some type of evidence included in the utterance that justifies this. However, in the Spanish version the narrator takes for granted that this event actually occurred and the translator ignores the judgement of the speaker in the original text, leading to a different interpretation.

7. DISCUSSION

The goal of the present study was to examine the translation of a set of modal verbs from English into Spanish in the literary text *Under the dome*. In this last section, the findings will be discussed by answering the research questions. Regarding the first research question (*Which linguistic devices are employed in the translation of epistemic modal markers from English into Spanish?*) the findings indicate that the most frequent translation in Spanish for the modal verb *might* is an adverbial equivalent. Three of the most frequent translations (*posiblemente, probablemente* and *quizás*) add up to 214 examples when the three categories are combined. Similarly, the modal verb *may* is translated into Spanish with verbal locutions, such as *es posible* and *puede ser que*, which also evaluate the probability of a proposition or a fact. On the other hand, verbs such as *could* or *can* have been translated frequently with its verbal auxiliary equivalent, as seen in Tables 3 and 4. However, one difference between English and Spanish is that in the later, the modal verbs can be inflected and show different tense, aspect and mood. Regarding the translation of *must*, Table 5 showed that the most frequent translation was also a modal auxiliary verb, such as *deber* or *tener que*.

With regard to the second question (*Do these devices show a similar pattern in both languages?*), the analysis of the translation of epistemic modality in the literary text *Under The Dome* shows that English and Spanish express the same pragmatic phenomenon with different linguistic devices, as seen in section 3 and in the analysis. Epistemic modality varies from English to Spanish, since subjectivity is a pragmatic notion that expresses the speakers attitude and his/her commitment with the degree of certainty of the proposition. The continuum that represents the gradable scale of certainty was frequently taken into account by the translator.

English shows a preference for the use of modal verbs to express epistemic modality, sometimes combined with other adverbial phrases or epistemic structures, whereas the Spanish version of the narrative tends to employ more adverbs, adverbial constructions, apart from some of the verbal auxiliary equivalent. Spanish also makes use of the subjunctive mood in subordinate clauses to convey the degree of certainty/uncertainty on the part of the speaker.

In addition, the results of the analysis show that the translator has sometimes ignored the epistemic meaning of the text in the SL, as observed in example (39) in which the Spanish

version includes and assertion about a fact, instead of an expression of a high degree of certainty on the part of the speaker.

Furthermore, aside from the examples discussed in the analysis section, it is worth noting that throughout the analysis the researcher has observed that, apart from core-modal verbs, semi-modal verbs and adverbs have also been used to express epistemic modality in King's work. One frequent semi-modal verbs used in the literary text was *need to* as in example (40) which was translated into the Spanish version of *La Cúpula* as *hiciera falta* or *hacía falta*:

- (40) English: Partly because he was so clearly Jim Rennie's man, partly because Randolph was sometimes harder than he **needed to be** [...]
Spanish: *En parte porque estaba claro que era un hombre de Jim Rennie y en parte porque a veces Randolph era más duro de lo que **hacía falta** [...]*

The use of modal adverbs is also very frequent in King's work. For example, during the extraction of the modal verb *may*, the researcher had to discard all of the examples of *maybe* detected by the search engine, as in example (41):

- (41) English: Or **maybe** it had been the day before, when they had listened to KC and the Sunshine Band instead of Jesus Radio.
Spanish: *O **quizá** anteayer, cuando todavía escuchaban a KC y la Sunshine Band en lugar de Radio Jesús.*

The most frequent translation of this adverb into Spanish was *quizá*, *tal vez* and *acaso*. Another adverb that expresses epistemic modality in English is *perhaps*, which is also translated into Spanish with adverbs *quizá*, *tal vez*. However, in example (42), the translation is *seguramente*:

- (42) English: This was **perhaps** a gibe, but Rennie, a sly old fish, did not rise to the bait.
Spanish: ***Seguramente** era una pulla, pero Rennie, pez viejo, no mordió el anzuelo.*

Modality is a semantic and pragmatic function described as the judgement of the speaker about the content of a proposition. In this case (example 42), the use of the evidential

seguramente leads to a slight semantic change in the Spanish translation, as the degree of uncertainty expressed by *perhaps* in English and *seguramente* in Spanish are different.

The present study confirms the findings of previous research about the translation of modal verbs from English into other languages. In the case of Spanish literary translation, the analysis indicates that the translator tried to transfer the original epistemic meaning of the English modal verb in most of the cases by using a modal verb equivalent, as well as other linguistic devices, such as adverbs, verbal constructions, or the selection of the subjunctive mood, which is more productive in Spanish regarding epistemic modality. In a few cases, the translator ignored the original epistemic meaning in which the speaker was including his/her opinion and the result of the translation varies from the original English text, as seen in the results section.

This study has contributed to the discipline by comparing the translation of modal verbs from English into Spanish and identifying the translational choices selected by the translator. The analysis confirms that translators explore different options to convey complex semantic and pragmatic meanings.

8. CONCLUSION

By combining a quantitative-qualitative analysis, this corpus-based study revealed some translation patterns that allowed the researcher to establish some parallelisms between the translation of modal verbs from English as the source language and Spanish as the target language. Moreover, this analysis is significant in the sense that a gap was observed in the previous literature regarding the semantic and pragmatic translation of epistemic modal verbs from Spanish into English. This research is significant because it contributes to the disciplines of Translation Studies and Contrastive Linguistics to assist future translators in the identification of epistemic modality and the different linguistic resources employed in this case study.

This study has its limitations, such as the categorization of *other forms* in the tables. As the classification of the forms was conducted manually by the author, some other interesting translations might have been dismissed due to the great number of tokens extracted from the original text. Future studies could make use of a parallel corpus to directly observe the correlations of the translations. Another limitation is related to the cases of the verb *must*. This research considered all the examples included in the original English work. However, the analysis might contain cases of modal auxiliaries where they have the function of a deontic modality.

Future studies could focus on the translation of other epistemic adverbs which are also frequent in King's work, such as *maybe* (translated into the Spanish version with different adverbial forms: such as *acaso*, *tal vez*, *quizá*), *probably*, or *possibly*. It would also be interesting to observe the translation of the adjective + preposition *apt to*, which was assigned an epistemic meaning by the translator, since it was very frequently translated as *quizá*. Future research could also use statistical methods in order to identify the correlation between the English and Spanish versions.

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